

ANALYSIS OF THE EFFECT OF WORK ACCIDENTS ON SOCIAL SECURITY SYSTEM

Aleyna Yaren ÜNLÜ

Istanbul Gelisim University, Istanbul Gelisim Vocational School, Occupational Health and Safety Program, Istanbul, Turkey

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3366-2564>

Mehmet Şükrü ÖZTANIK

Istanbul Gelisim University, Istanbul Gelisim Vocational School, Occupational Health and Safety Program, Istanbul, Turkey

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8141-3994>

Assist. Prof. Dr. Kaan KOÇALI

Istanbul Gelisim University, Istanbul Gelisim Vocational School, Occupational Health and Safety Program, Istanbul, Turkey

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1329-6176>

Abstract

As a result of the rapid development of technology after the Industrial Revolution, the focus of production on machines, the acceleration of social transformation, the decrease and/or disappearance of the importance of existing formations and values; occupational diseases and work accidents that occur due to people working for long periods in factories where health and safety measures are not taken have become a major problem among the public over time. Work accidents are a phenomenon that accompanies all human activities and are one of the basic health and economic problems of modern societies.

Their results affect not only the injured workers but also their families, work organization and society as a whole. In order to minimize the results of work accidents that occur, first of all, the data must be recorded in a healthy way. For this reason, analyzing the recorded work accidents causes possible work accidents to be prevented with a proactive approach. In this context, it is of great importance to examine and interpret the work accidents experienced in our country. Reducing work accidents and the costs resulting from the incident and creating healthy and safe working conditions in workplaces is possible with work safety management. In the management of occupational safety activities, the examination and analysis of occupational accident statistical data guides the occupational safety study to be carried out.

The relationship between occupational safety and social insurance plays a critical role in protecting employees against risks they may be exposed to at work. While occupational safety is defined as the set of measures taken to ensure that employees work in a safe and healthy environment, social insurance aims to compensate for the financial losses that employees may encounter as a result of

such risks. The social insurance system provides compensation and health services to employees in the event of occupational accidents and occupational diseases, thus ensuring their economic protection. This encourages employers to take occupational safety measures seriously, as reducing occupational accidents contributes to lower insurance premiums and lowering the costs of the enterprise. In addition, occupational safety and social insurance complement each other in order to increase the well-being of employees and promote safe working conditions at the workplace. The effective implementation of occupational safety measures contributes to the prevention of occupational accidents and occupational diseases, which reduces the financial burden on the social insurance system. In addition, compensation and health services provided within the scope of social insurance support the rehabilitation of employees exposed to occupational accidents or occupational diseases and their return to the workforce. Thus, the strong relationship between occupational safety and social insurance creates a mechanism that protects the long-term interests of both employees and employers.

Within the scope of the study, the statistical data of the Social Security Institution (SSI) regarding occupational accidents were individually researched and grouped on an annual basis. All legal parameters such as gender, age range, education status, work experience, province of residence of individuals who had an occupational accident; number of occupational accidents, how many people they affected, sector, what kind of injury occurred to the individual, number of deaths, periods of disability, etc. were individually grouped and analyzed. Using annual data, occupational accident severity rates and occupational accident frequency rates were calculated for each year without any sector distinction. Thus, the annual status of occupational accidents in Turkey was revealed and their impact on the social insurance system was examined.

The study was prepared within the scope of the project titled “*Investigating the 20-Year Profile of Work Accidents and Occupational Diseases and Their Effects on Work and Insurance Life: Comparison of Turkey and Europe-27 Region*” numbered 1919B012335533, which is carried out within the scope of TUBITAK 2209-A University Students Research Projects Support Program.

Key Words: Occupational Health and Safety, Work Accident, Social Security, Social Policy.